

A COMPLETE MICROSTRUCTURAL AND MECHANICAL CHARACTERIZATION OF BAMBOO TECHNICAL AND ELEMENTARY FIBERS

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1 Introduction

Bamboo fibers are an attractive alternative to reinforce polymers in the new era of green composite materials. Bamboo fibers have been scarcely used due to the difficulty in extracting high quality technical fibers. In the current research project a mechanical process has been developed to extract undamaged long technical fibers from the Colombian species *Guadua angustifolia*. The average modulus of these fibers is 43 GPa ($\pm 2.5\%$) and the strength reaches 800 MPa ($\pm 15\%$). To fully explore these excellent mechanical properties and to make an adequate use of this new material as reinforcement, it is indispensable to have a complete understanding of fiber behavior as a function of the microstructure.

2 Materials and testing methods

The bamboo culms (species *Guadua angustifolia* Kunth) were extracted from a typical bamboo plantation in Colombia, specifically from the Coffee Region at the National Research Center for Guadua where the environmental conditions are: 1.240 meters above sea level, a temperature of 25°C and relative humidity of 80%. Bamboo technical fibers were extracted from the bamboo culms giving a maximum technical fiber length between 20 and 35 cm and a diameter between 90 and 250 μm (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1: Technical bamboo fibres

2.1 Microscopic observations

SEM observations were made on transverse sections of the culm in order to investigate the distribution of the vascular bundles as well as the microstructure of the fiber wall. Samples (1cm³) were cut using a sledge microtome (Reichert, Vienna, Austria) in order to preserve all the surface features and to avoid artefacts that can appear after grinding or polishing techniques. After treating with a bleaching agent, the samples were rinsed and dehydrated in an ethanol series (50, 75 and finally 96%), followed by gold-coating and observed using a scanning electron microscope (SEM), Philips XL 30 FEG.

Thin sections for light microscope (LM) observations were made to observe the layering structure of the wall of the elementary fibers. Small samples (1mm^3) were progressively infiltrated with LR white (LRW). Sections $5\mu\text{m}$ thick were produced.

2.1 Microfibril angle

The angle of the microfibrils in the primary and secondary wall layer of bamboo elementary fibers was determined based on a new technique developed by Wang [1].

2.2 Sample preparation and tensile test for single technical fibers

Single fiber tensile tests at gauge lengths of 2, 5, 10, 25 and 40 mm were performed on a mini tensile testing machine developed in the Department of Metallurgy and Materials Engineering at KU Leuven.

Short span tensile tests of technical fibers at gauge lengths of 0.5, 1 and 2 mm were performed on a TA Instruments Q800 Dynamic Mechanical Analyzer (DMA), with a Film Tension Clamp.

Both experiments were performed following the methodology described in [2]. Experiments are performed on a range of test spans, to allow determining an extrapolated E-modulus at infinite span length. This way the effect of slippage in the clamps can be filtered out. Also, by determining a system compliance, strain values can be corrected for slippage.

2.3 Estimation of the Young's Modulus of elementary bamboo fibers.

To correlate the fiber microstructure with the mechanical properties, the technical bamboo fiber is considered as a unidirectional (UD) short fiber composite (SFC). The elastic modulus of elementary bamboo fiber is predicted based on the Cox model [3-5] and the Halpin-Tsai equations [6, 7],

2.4 Transverse fiber properties

Bamboo fiber composites were tested in transverse flexural 3PBT and transverse tensile test in order to assess transverse technical fiber properties.

Unidirectional bamboo fiber/epoxy composites were produced using vacuum infusion. Based on sample dimensions and the desired fiber volume fraction, the amount of fibers that need to be placed in the mould can be calculated. A fiber volume fraction of approx. 40% was used.

Transverse flexural 3PBTs and Transverse Tensile tests were performed according to the ASTM D790M and ASTM 3039 respectively.

3 Results and discussion

3.1 Study of fiber microstructure

The technical fibers (bean-shaped) attached to the conductive supporting tissue are the mechanical support of the bamboo culm; they consist of many elementary fibers connected by lignin called middle lamellae (Fig.2).

Fig. 2: Bamboo fiber bundle; upon fibre extraction the bundle splits up in a few technical fibres, each consisting of several elementary fibres

The elementary bamboo fibers exhibit a hexagonal or pentagonal shape; the small hole in the centre of each elementary fiber is called lumen. As mentioned before, each elementary bamboo fiber wall possesses a unique multilayer configuration called polylamellate structure (Fig.3), where every layer is reinforced with cellulose microfibrils at different

angles. This structure determines the mechanical properties of the technical fibers and contributes to the strength and modulus of the bamboo culm.

In agreement with other researches [8-11], the polylamellate structure or multilayering of the elementary fibers for *Guadua angustifolia* is more visible in the periphery of the fiber bundle where the elementary fiber wall has in general 2 to 4 layers (Fig. 4).

Fig. 3: Polylamellate structure of elementary bamboo fibers.

Fig. 4: Elementary bamboo fiber where multiple layering is not visible

3.2 Microfibril angle

Figure 5 shows a detail of the secondary wall of an elementary fiber, after chemical treatment where the primary wall has been etched away. The orientation of the micro-fibrils is close to 0 degrees in agreement with [9].

Fig. 5 Microfibrils of the secondary wall

3.3 Mechanical properties of long technical fibers

Fiber mechanical properties have been studied at 4 different span lengths (5, 10, 25, 40 mm) to determine the fiber quality after the extraction process and the mechanical performance of the new material. The tensile strength has a small variation as a function of the span length and remains at about 800 MPa (Fig. 6). The Young's Modulus is on average 43 GPa. In terms of specific properties, normalized to the density, they can be compared with glass fibers [2].

Fig. 6: Tensile strength of bamboo technical fibers.

Fig. 7: Estimated Young's modulus of elementary bamboo fibers.

3.4 Mechanical properties of elementary bamboo fibers

The mechanical properties such as strength and Young's modulus of the elementary fiber were predicted based on a novel approach that combines the micromechanics of composite materials, commonly used for unidirectional short fiber composites and the fiber microstructure. The estimated Young's Modulus of the elementary fiber is 50 GPa (Fig. 7) for an aspect ratio (length/diameter) larger than 38.

Short span tensile tests were performed on technical fibers in order to validate the predicted values. Experimental results are in agreement with the predicted values. The orientation close to 0 degrees of the microfibrils of the secondary wall explains the high longitudinal stiffness of bamboo fibers.

Fig. 8: Young's Modulus of elementary bamboo fibres, experimental values

Also, the failure modes of single fibers after tensile testing were analyzed by microscopic observations, to have an indication of the stress development in the elementary fibers and the different failure mechanisms. In the failure mode of Fig. 9, the technical fiber was split and the failure occurred along or inside the primary layer where the microfibrils are oriented at an angle of 90°. In Fig. 10 an elementary fiber was pulled out from the technical fiber.

Fig. 9: Failure along the primary layer of elementary fiber.

Fig. 10: Elementary fiber pull-out.

3.5 Study of the anisotropy of bamboo technical fibers

Until now, longitudinal properties of single bamboo fibers have been studied showing that this new reinforcement possesses good mechanical properties.

Nevertheless, in the case of natural fibers, it is widely known that they have a complex anisotropic structure which influences the transverse and shear behavior of the final composite. Information about this aspect is scarce and therefore needs to be investigated.

Bamboo fiber composite (epoxy resin)	90° (tensile)	90° (flexural)
E(GPa)	2,72±0,32	2,7±0,2

Table. 1. Transverse Young's modulus of bamboo fiber/epoxy composites.

Table 1 shows the transverse Young's modulus of bamboo fiber/epoxy composites, calculated from the transverse flexural and tensile tests. In both cases the value of the Young's modulus is close to the Young's modulus of the pure resin which is typical for a matrix dominated test.

Assuming isostrain condition during the complete tests, bamboo technical fiber transverse modulus is determined at 2,66 GPa by back calculating from the composite behavior using the Halpin-Tsai equations. Results reveal that the technical fiber is highly anisotropic and the lignin layer that connects the elementary fibers acting as the matrix material, is the main responsible for the low transverse properties of the technical fiber.

3. Conclusions

The hierarchical structure of bamboo fibers can be described with the help of the micromechanics of composite materials.

In general, the results of this study suggest that there is a good potential for long bamboo technical fibers as reinforcing material for polymeric matrices and that the material could be appropriate to be used for commercial applications, where the fulfillment of environmental regulations and weight reduction are important aspects.

The elementary fiber has a Young's modulus of around 50 GPa, which is both found by back-calculating from technical fiber modulus and experimentally by conducting very short span single fiber tensile tests.

Microstructural observations reveal that the cellulose microfibrils of the elementary fibers have predominantly 0 degree orientation, combined with a

thin outer primary wall layer of the elementary fibres with 90 degree orientation.

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